

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SPORT MANAGEMENT INNOVATIONS AND THE ISSUES IN THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA

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Abstract

Volatile and uncertain environment creates significant challenges for traditional organizational structures and managerial approaches. Sport management is one of the key areas requiring a special focus, especially taking into consideration current key trends of digitalization, human capital development, population's mindset and personal priorities changes. Additionally special need for innovations in sport management are created by Armenian specific context and national priorities in this field. The aim of this article is to identify special aspects of innovations' management within Armenian sports sector. The paper studies specific prerequisites and environment for design and implementation of strategic change in terms of Armenian sport management. Armenia's current context, namely socio-economic future growth and digitalization strategy are considered as key prerequisites for a developed innovative approach towards managing the national sports sector. Key areas for innovation in sport management are outlined. Need for incorporating the innovation management component into professional development programs in Armenia is stressed. Conducted research pays special attention to the need for adequate managerial framework as a major enabler for innovation management's adoption in Armenian sport industry. The comprehensive framework is outlined for more efficient innovative management in Armenian sports sector. The proposed comprehensive framework consists of three interconnected blocks, namely, Collaborative Problem Solving; Agile Development and Implementation; Human Capital Enhancement. The research stresses need for both organizational and personnel skills being developed for supporting strategic change in Armenian sport industry. Professionals and researchers in the field of innovations in sport management, thinktanks, professional associations, public authorities, international sport institutions, may use the conducted research. Further research lies in the field of expanded stakeholder analysis including wider groups considering innovation management for Armenian sports sector; another issue for further research is design and adapting inter-disciplinary toolkits for supporting innovation management in Armenian sport industry.

Keywords: Armenian sports sector; innovations; organizational model; stakeholder; Agile.

Introduction. Context of high uncertainty creates a number of challenges and opportunities for traditional management models. Sport management is no exception to this issue. Under some circumstances sports sector is pushed forward taking innovative approaches in order to ensure its long-term development and value creation for vast groups of stakeholders. Armenian current context of enhanced socio-economic future growth enabled by digitalization strategy and other innovative approaches at both macro- and micro-level supports this agenda for future sport industry development – both in its growth opportunities and prerequisites for this growth. Hence, these outlined issues condition the need for an efficient way for developing and implementing innovation management in Armenian sport industry under current challenges.

Literature Review. Number of papers is dedicated to studying organizational and infrastructural issues in supporting innovation management in sport industry. In this context Marlier, Constandt, Schyvinck, De Bock, Winand, Willem [1, p. 142-144] analyze issues of capacity linkage in terms of innovative development of sport industry. In turn, Marlier, Lucidarme, Cardon, De Bourdeaudhuij, Babiak, Willem [2, p. 1306] consider cross-sector partnership framework in managing innovation in sport industry. Winand, Scheerder, Vos, Zintz [3, p. 290-292] analyzing policy-making framework for

supporting innovations in sport industry (based on example of regional sport organizations), expand this body of research. Additionally, Kasale, Winand, Morrow [4, p. 228-230] research stakeholder approach to managing innovations in sport organizations (based on Botswana example). Further, Dobbels, Voets, Marlier, De Waegeneer, Willem [5, p. 575-576] analyze network structures in managing innovations in sport industry. These results are of high importance for the conducted research in the context of developing an adequate framework for both short-term and long-term success of developed and implemented change in Armenian sport industry.

Body of research studies issues of developing innovation management for sports in disadvantaged areas. Marlier, Van Dyck, Cardon, De Bourdeaudhuij, Babiak, Willem [6, p. 140196] consider social capital component in promoting innovative sport management for disadvantaged communities. Research [7, p. 115-1116] studies management approaches based on capacity building towards promoting sports in disadvantaged communities. These above-mentioned research papers are crucial in understanding the strategic needs of sport industry in developing countries with a special consideration of challenges faced by the industry, public authorities, and other stakeholders in both designing and implementing change.

Number of papers studies toolkits for supporting innovation management for sport industry. In this context, paper [8, p. 211-212] considers communication tools in managing innovative sport model. In turn, Winand, Fergusson [9, p. 968-970] study technological tools in managing innovative models for sport industry. Those results are employed in this research in part of developing a calibrated toolkit for innovation management in Armenian sport industry, in particular under agile methodology aspect.

A separate body of research analyzes issues of human capital in managing innovation in sport industry. Winand, Anagnostopoulos [10, p. 580-582] consider issues of motivating personnel in respect of implementing service innovation in sport organizations. Further, Delshab, Winand, Sadeghi Boroujerdi, Pyun, Mahmoudian [11, p. 670-671] analyze human capital component in managing innovations in sport organizations. These results are used in the conducted research in studying the human capital role in developing and implementing innovations for sport industry in Armenia focused on its higher efficiency in long-term.

Number of papers is dedicated to peculiarities of sport management in Armenian specific context. Hovhannisyan [12, p. 148-149] analyzes peculiarities of Armenian society post-soviet transformation in different sectors with a focus on an individual, personal

needs and motivations. Research [13] studies issues of Armenia's transformation with a focus on new organizational models in different sectors on micro- and macro-level. Babayan [14, p. 167] researches social-psychological issues of sport sector within transforming course of Armenian society. Avanesov [15, p. 18-19] studies issues of human capital preparation for the purposes of supporting innovative environment in sport industry, namely, in sport management education.

However, issues of innovative sport management under Armenian context in terms of a sufficient organizational and methodic toolkit is not studied sufficiently in the existing body of research.

Method of this article is peculiarities of managing innovation in sport industry of Armenia within the context of its toolkit enabling efficient development and implementation under current environment.

Results. Armenia as any other state under modern socio-economic conditions has relative issues in terms of physical inactivity level of its population (Figure 1). In this context, WHO estimates Armenia's direct healthcare costs attributable to NCDs and mental health issues associated with physical inactivity as USD 4.5 million per year, and cumulative for 2020-2030 period at USD 49.0 million [16].

Figure 1. Level of physical inactivity (under WHO methodology) among population groups in Armenia, Germany, the U.S., %, 2022

Source: compiled by author based on data [16].

WHO [16] additionally outlines a need for stronger knowledge and mindset communication campaigns – both in terms of national physical activities communication campaigns and national mass participation activities. This campaign has to be reinforced by promoting physical activity in all environments – at workplace, at primary and secondary educational institutions, community sports, public and inclusive spaces [16].

In turn, that poses a need for active environment development. That requires an adequate policy and infrastructure as its key enablers. These measures have to be developed within a holistic approach taking into account interests of vast groups of stakeholders, i.e.

youth, adults, seniors, disabled people, others. Innovative managerial solutions based on technology (first of all, digitalization) have to be leveraged in planning and development of the outlined solutions in terms of active environment in Armenia benefiting higher rates of physical activity and sport-oriented mindset among population.

Therefore, sport sector has to be one of the key priorities for Armenia in terms of building its long-term success in respect of high quality of human capital. This national-level endeavor could be successfully realized through efficient planning and implementation of sport management innovation.

In this context, sport management innovation is a key discussion area for both researchers and professionals in governmental, private and non-governmental structures in Armenia. In particular, the recent forum “Innovation in Practice: People in Center” [17] held in November 2022 outlines a need for developing innovation in Armenia focused on human capital component.

This initiative aimed to evaluate the efforts and achievements of Armenian public sector’s innovators; additionally new approaches to solving public sector’s key issues were outlined on that platform. A particular focus is directed towards designing and realizing an effective cooperation model encompassing vast groups of stakeholders, i.e., public authorities, non-governmental organizations, thinktanks, international organizations and financing donors. Such an organizational model is aimed at better planning and implementing innovations in Armenian public sector, including sport sector.

In particular, it is emphasized that Armenian innovation sector requires approaches and tools to navigate and thrive in uncertainty both at micro- and macro-levels. Thus, the innovation ecosystem has to be remodeled taking into account key bottlenecks and barriers of different nature. Specifically, such an ecosystem must connect different sectors, both public and private, aimed at increasing collective capacity to innovate and take creative approaches towards key challenges in governmental sector, including Armenian sports sector needs for strategic long-term development according to the national goals and priorities.

Special focus has to be dedicated to State Plan for the Development of Education of the Republic of Armenia till 2030 developed and presented by Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Armenia in 2022 [18]. Developments Plan’s core is designing and implementing changes in Armenia’s human capital through promoting knowledge and creativity, based on

continuous education. Such an approach has to be taken also in respect of physical development of Armenian citizens based on wellbeing goals and the corresponding framework.

Considering public authorities’ major initiatives, another driver for sport management innovations is Armenia’s Digitalization Strategy for 2021-2025 developed and implemented by Ministry of High-Tech Industry [19]. Particular focus of this strategic plan is on digital transformation aimed at promoting effective and transparent public sector management based on data. This digitalization initiative also has to encompass changes in Armenian sport industry. Therefore, national digitalization strategy has to be translated into sport management innovation employed in Armenia. It has to be stressed, that such a strategic approach has to be adopted on both developing and implementation stages of the process in terms of strategic change of the field in question.

In this context, we have to outline the major areas for innovation in sport management, i.e. organizational, technological, social, commercial innovations. In general, these directions encompass key areas of innovation activities in governmental, private, non-governmental sectors, including sport industry. That gives ground for employing both general and specific managerial approaches and toolkits towards sport management innovations. It has to be stressed, that these innovation directions have to be taken into account in developing a holistic approach towards transforming Armenian sport industry with a special focus on its strategic goals and challenges. More specifically – in planning and implementing Armenian sport management innovation with a focus on achieving both short-term, and long-term strategic goals and national priorities. These areas in respect of sport management innovations are presented in more detail in Table 1.

Table 1

Key areas for innovation in sport management

<i>Area of innovation</i>	<i>Comment</i>
Organizational	Changes in the way organizations in sport industry are being structured and functioning
Technological	Adoption of new technologies both in sports and its administration
Social	Development on new approaches towards sport management industry incorporating social purpose, i.e. disadvantaged areas
Commercial	Employing innovative component in developing sport industry under commercial paradigm

Source: developed by author based on [1-8].

Special attention has to be paid to preparing specialists in the field of sport management oriented at efficient innovation’s development and implementation. Recent research [15, p. 18-19] based on benchmark analysis of Armenian and European sport management university educational programs outlines a sizeable gap in respect of innovation management component in Armenian sport management. Specifically, research [15, p. 18-19] indicates lack of capabilities in innovation management as a key driver of supporting both short-term and long-term growth in Armenian sports industry.

Summing up, there are significant challenges which Armenian sport industry affecting it both in

short-term and long-term in multiple interconnected aspects. Hence, capabilities have to be developed and supported for efficient innovation management – in particular, in the infrastructural and methodical respects. That would lay a foundation for truly efficient model in respect of innovative development of Armenian sport industry.

In this light the traditional managerial architecture of Armenian sport industry has to be rebuilt with a focus on *organizational innovation-based culture*. That would make the implemented change long-lasting and benefiting vast groups of stakeholders. Organizational innovation-based culture is defined as a conceptualized environment cultivating leadership on multiple organi-

zational levels focused on nurturing innovation development and implementation on a continuous basis [20, p. 106]. Thus, changes on multiple levels have to be designed and implemented in order to support this holistic structure.

Under such an approach both structure-wise and purpose-wise dimensions have to be focused through specific organizational mechanism on the purpose of nurturing and supporting innovation. In the practical respect that provides for less barriers and less complexity within the organization. That, in turn, transforms into greater passion and higher sense of purpose on behalf of the personnel and other stakeholders.

In this context, the key enabler of the organizational innovation-based culture is *interprofessional interdisciplinary teams*, i.e. a group of professionals of different level and different background brought to the project from key sectors with a purpose of creating a cutting-edge innovation and significant change to the field in question. Interprofessional and interdisciplinary teams benefit stakeholders in a number of ways, namely:

- Higher quality delivered;
- Faster implementation of solutions;
- Complex problem solving;
- Better interaction both inside and outside the project team;
- Less friction within the team (less attention paid to titles, ranks, etc. – which enables faster implementation and more creativity);

- Project team member's better entitlement due to their innovative capabilities.

In the light of this, a comprehensive model has to be formed based on the innovation management approaches. The model in question has to be relevant and reflect both key tasks and management needs in terms of developing and implementing innovations for sport industry. This model consists of the following blocks:

- *Block 1*: Collaborative Problem Solving;
- *Block 2*: Agile Development and Implementation;
- *Block 3*: Human Capital Enhancement.

Further, the outlined blocks are described in more detail.

Block 1. Collaborative problem solving is a critical approach towards developing and implementing innovations. Under high uncertainty, environment organizations have to take a structured approach towards dealing with strategic developments. Collaborative problem solving approach also takes into account increased speed of change, resulting in high relevance of this management toolkit.

Collaborative problem solving is especially important under post-pandemic environment – in respect of interpersonal communication, soft skills development, stimulating higher stakeholder engagement. That also allows to taking a structured approach towards complex problems aimed at stakeholders adopting the proposed change. Collaborative problem solving process is summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Collaborative problem solving process

Source: developed by author based on [20].

Block 2. Agile Development and Implementation. In practical respect, the outlined above prerequisites for supporting innovative model for sport industry require a working managerial approach, such as Agile. This methodology operates in Sprints – being a short in time-defined set of doable tasks within a larger aim in respect of realizing a specific project [22]. In general, Agile may be considered as a set of values and organizational philosophy approach aimed at fast and efficient implementation under volatile environment.

Efficient application of agile approach requires an adequate infrastructure, namely:

- Development and delivery infrastructure;
- Continuous learning infrastructure;
- Collective ownership infrastructure;
- Integration and communication infrastructure.

Hence, agile methodology is a key enabler for efficient innovation development and implementation, in

particular for sport industry. That is made possible through its methodology, which acts on multiple organizational levels encompassing vast groups of stakeholders. Being a mindset rather than a strict set of rules, Agile softly directs and nurtures the innovative environment and enables fast and efficient implementation of change.

Block 3. Human Capital Enhancement. Effective implementation of sport management innovations in Armenia requires a strong basis in a form of an adequate human capital model. That is a critical component of successful acceptance of changes and further long-term development of the innovative sport management. This human capital model is comprised of a set of skills. The required set of skills within the human capital component in respect of sport management innovations is presented on Figure 3 [23].

Figure 3. Human capital model in respect of a robust sport innovation management model
Source: developed by author based on [23].

The mentioned above human capital model is focused on a set of skills – both of hard and soft nature. Hard skills reflect technical ability to perform required tasks in respect of sport management innovations. In turn, soft skills within the human capital model represent an individual's ability to comprehend colleagues, demonstrate emotional intelligence, etc. This behavioral and interpersonal skills set reinforces the technical abilities' performance. That also supports teamwork approach and enhances engagement into the process of building a sport innovation management model in Armenia. Communication component of the successful change management framework also heavily relies on the outlined human capital model. Due to these optimal skills' set trust and commitment towards the changes is reinforced for both external and internal groups of stakeholders. Hence, that is a critical requisition for a long-term success of sport management innovations' implementation on both micro- and macro-level.

Discussion & Conclusions. Summing up, the performed research outlines the key role of innovations in accelerating sport industry development under challenges of volatile environment on both macro- and micro-level in Armenia. These challenges are various by

its nature and pose both significant threats and opportunities for Armenian sport industry development. Consequently, such a situation requires an appropriate framework for innovation sport management aimed at efficient and long-term development in the field.

Adequate managerial framework is a key prerequisite for supporting innovation management in sport industry. The proposed managerial framework for sport management in Armenia encompasses 1. Collaborative Problem Solving; 2. Agile Development and Implementation; 3. Human Capital Enhancement. A blend of both organizational (aimed at problem solving, designing change and efficiently implementing it) and personnel skills (encompassing emotional intelligence, social interaction and leadership capabilities) is critical for supporting innovations in the researched field. Long-term success for the developed and implemented initiatives is impossible without engagement and support on behalf of the personnel and other stakeholders.

Further research lies in the field of deeper stakeholder analysis considering wider groups in respect of innovation management for sport industry. Additionally, an issue has to be further researched on adopting

inter-disciplinary toolkits for supporting innovation management in sport industry.

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